

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

ECONOMIC INDICATORS AND PRODUCTIVITY OF NEWLY INTRODUCED PEACH VARIETIES TO AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

To study the development characteristics of fruit plants and to create favorable conditions for the plant, it is necessary to know the phylogenetic development of that plant. The individual development of plants is called ontogenesis. This development begins with the formation of the zygote and ends with its complete destruction. Stems and branches become thicker as a result of the growth of cambium tissue cells in plants. Suitable soil and climate conditions are necessary for the normal development and growth of fruit plants. Plants go through 4 main stages of growth and development during the period of activity: rapid growth, weak development; poor growth, rapid development; rapid growth, rapid development and poor growth, poor development.

Keywords: peach varieties, fertility, crop, growth, vegetative shoots

Based on the information of I.V. Michuri, C.M. Aliyev states that there are 4 main development periods in the ontogenetic development of plants as embryonic, youth, fertility and destruction, and also 9 age periods in fruit plants based on the information of P.G. Shit [1,2],[3]. Embryonic development continues from the formation of the zygote in the plant to the formation of true leaves from the seed. In different plants, this period continues for different periods, apple, pear, etc. it lasts 10-20 years in plants, and 6-7 years in peach plants. The period of fruiting begins when the plants bear their first crop, The period of growth or growth of the vegetative parts begins with the formation of the plant and continues until it produces its first crop. This period is accompanied by rapid development of vegetative parts and root system in fruit plants. The productive period starts from the time of the first harvest and continues until the plant starts to weaken and dry. The growth and harvest period in plants is characterized by the growth of fruit branches, the growth of vegetative shoots, but relatively short in length.

As with all fruit plants, the development of the peach plant is characterized by 2 periods: relative rest and vegetation period. In deciduous trees and shrubs, the phase of relative dormancy begins with leaf shedding and lasts until the period of bud swelling. In these plants, it occurs as a result of the weakening of the intensity of the physiological-biochemical processes in the cell protoplasm and the changes in the metabolism. Although the plant retains its appearance during the dormant period, flowers, leaves, pods and fruits do not form on it. However, although many physiological processes such as respiration, transpiration and metabolism continue, the speed of these processes is slow. A period of relative dormancy is observed in both tissues and shoots. Thus, in the peach plant, shortly after fertilization, the embryo develops and forms through the process of division, and the plant again transitions to the period of dormancy. It can be concluded that the phase of relative rest in plant ontogeny is first observed in the zygote. Physiologists

divide the period of relative dormancy in fruit and berry plants into 3 half-periods: the beginning of the period of relative dormancy, natural (physiological, organic, or deep) and forced relative dormancy. At this stage, the intensity of metabolism weakens, the growth of meristem tissues in the top shoot stops, and the accumulation of starch in the tissues reaches its maximum, while the activity of the cambium gradually stops from the tip of the umbrella, from the top to the bottom, and finally stops at the root throat. Plants need a temperature of 0°C, and most fruit and berry plants need a temperature of +5...+7°C to pass the natural dormancy period [4,5].

The different climatic conditions of the fall season, which cause senescence attenuation, change the resorption time and efficiency compared to normal senescence, leading to higher concentrations in dormant organs [2,6]. As noted by many authors [7], the basis of the period of relative rest is the cessation of division in the meristem tissues of the plant and the weakening of physiological processes during the development of vegetative organs along with changes in metabolism. According to observations, a period of relative rest begins when the air temperature drops below + 10°C, and this period ends when the temperature rises in early spring and the shoots begin to develop. In the autumn rainy years, excess irrigation and excessive use of nitrogenous fertilizers lead to a long period of relative rest, and if drought is observed, excessive use of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers causes this phase to be shortened. According to the observations of T.A. Latsko, damage of stone fruit plants by winter frosts in the period of relative silence is 7.3% in cherry, 19.7% in plum, 80.5% in peach and 95.7% in apricot [6,11]. In the peach varieties that we observed, no damage from winter frosts was observed in the phase of relative rest. In the life of plants, the stage of relative calmness is of special importance. Because at this stage, there are favorable conditions for the implementation of agrotechnical measures (fertilizing, shaping and pruning, moving the plant

from one area to another, fighting against diseases and pests, etc.) that play an important role in the life of the plant. During the research years, the relative dormancy phase lasted 112-142 days for the varieties, 123-135 days on average. This period is the same (129 days) in Netix 28, Netix 34, Redix 2-110 varieties as compared to the control variety (Fedai), Melox 26, Netix 25, Redix 25, Maliks 25, Redix 27 and Garteiro varieties (130-135 days). long, while in other varieties (123-128 days) it lasted relatively short. The duration of the relative rest period was the least in Maliks 145 (123 days) and the longest in Netix 25 (135 days) compared to the control (Fedai) and other research varieties.

The productivity of the varieties is considered one of the important indicators in the evaluation of the economic and biological characteristics of the introduced peach varieties. The study of the productivity of fruit plants makes it possible to determine the potential of the variety. E. Gür and D. Erogul, as a result of their research on the peach plant, came to the conclusion that the application of hiberrelc acid not only increases the weight and caliber of the fruits, but also causes an increase in the hardness of the rind and the amount of dry matter soluble in water [3]. A. V. Smykov, O. S. Fyodorova and others. in their articles, they note that the productivity of the Ambergold peach variety is related to the temperature of the air during flowering, and the productivity of the Golden variety is related to the capacity percentage of generative shoots, and the productivity of these varieties is negatively affected by powdery mildew and leaf curl disease. The authors came to the conclusion that in Armgold and Springgold peach varieties, 97-100% of fruits are formed mainly in mixed racemes, in Zempush, Kardinal and Baby Gold-7 varieties, 25% are formed in bouquets, and 75% in mixed racemes [8]. E. Er, A. Koç and E. Aydin, when selecting the varieties according to the yield per tree, note that the Early Red variety has the highest value with 21.70 kg/tree, and the Mycrest variety with the lowest value with 4.91 kg/tree [35, p. 280]. The peach plant is a very early-harvesting plant, many varieties bear fruits in the 2nd-3rd year [105, p.18]. While studying the effect of the given food area and canopy shape on productivity, the employees of the Crimean Agro-Technological University came to the conclusion that the 7-8-year-old Red Haven variety with an improved canopy shape was 98.1 cents/ha, free palmette, compared to the control option in gardens with a 5×3 m planting pattern. 135.8 cents/ha in shaped gardens and 136.6 cents/ha in truncated pyramidal gardens. In the 6x3 and 6x2 m planting scheme on the AP-1 plot, the Red Haven peach trees were given a V-type umbrella shape, at which time the productivity of the plant per hectare was 198 sen/ha [6,9]. Some authors in their works [9.10] note that the productivity of the peach plant depends on the area of the leaf surface and the number of plants per unit area, in addition to the food area. According to those records, the leaf surface area of 5.0 x 1.5 m planting pattern gardens under observation is 11.9 m², the yield is 9.6 t/ha, and the leaf surface area is 16.2 m² in the 5.0 x 2.0 m planting pattern gardens. m², productivity was 7.2 t/ha. The increase in the number of trees per unit area

and the application of technologically modern cultivation methods lead to an increase in productivity. N.A. Babintseva notes that when a more dense planting scheme (1666-2500 trees/ha) is used, when the trees are given the form of a leading branch and a bush-shaped umbrella, the productivity is from 15.4 t/ha to 26.0 t/ha.

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